

IMPORTANCE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN THE TREATMENT OF ACNE VULGARIS

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Annotation. Acne is a skin condition associated with the activation of the sebaceous glands, enlarged and blocked sebaceous glands. Where the sebaceous gland on the skin is blocked, bacteria begin to multiply. Bacteria cause inflammation and swelling in this area. Acne vulgaris is the most common inflammatory, chronic, recurrent disease of the sebaceous follicular apparatus localized on the face, back, and various parts of the body. Varying degrees of acne occur in 80-85% of people between the ages of 12 and 25 and in 11% of people over the age of 25.

Key words. *Acne vulgaris, Propionibacterium acnes, Staphylococcus epidermidis, skin diseases, medicinal plants.*

Purpose. To study the medicinal plants that can be used in the treatment of acne vulgaris based on literature data.

The results. Acne vulgaris is one of the most common dermatological diseases in the world among skin diseases [1; 5]. It usually occurs in almost everyone during a person's life. The pathogenesis of acne is complex and depends on the following four main factors: increased activity of the sebaceous glands under the influence of androgen hormones, follicular hyperkeratinization, colonization of the bacterium *Propionibacterium acnes* (an anaerobic bacterium that is a normal component of the skin microflora), and inflammation [6]. Due to the effect of androgen hormones, the high amount of oil produced by the sebaceous glands leads to the proliferation of the bacterium *Propionibacterium acnes* in the ducts of the skin glands, and this proliferation produces anti-inflammatory cytokines, interleukin-1b (IL-1b), IL-8, induces the production of granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), and complement. In addition to *Propionibacterium acnes* bacteria, *Pityrosporum ovale* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* are also present in acne as the main causative microorganisms. There are 3 types of acne: comedonal, nodular and papulopustular. Comedonal type acne shrinks without inflammation, while nodular and papulopustular acne

shrinks with inflammation [2]. A variety of medications are available to treat acne vulgaris, including antibiotics, retinoids, and hormonal therapy.

The use of natural medicines, especially plants, began thousands of years ago. In the last decade, there has been an increasing interest in medicinal plants due to their increasing resistance to existing antimicrobial agents, side effects and sometimes high cost of treatment. *Abies koreana* essential oil has a strong antibacterial effect against drug-sensitive and resistant *Propionibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. In addition, *Abies koreana* essential oil reduces the lipopolysaccharide-induced secretion of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, nitric oxide (NO) and prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), suggesting the anti-inflammatory effects of *Abies koreana* essential oil. shows [7]. Some Indian medicinal plants such as *Ammonia baccifera*, *Hibiscus syriacus*, *Quercus infectoria*, *Berberis aristata*, *Couroupita guianensis*, *Symplocos racemosa* and *Mucuna pruriens* have excellent antibacterial inhibitory effects. In addition, the ethanol extract of *Symplocos racemosa* has the highest activity due to the presence of antibacterial alkaloids. *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Coscinium fenestratum*, *Tephrosia purpurea*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Symplocos racemosa*, *Curcubito pepo* and *Eclipta alba* have been found to have a strong inhibitory effect against *Propionibacterium acne* [3; 4].

Conclusion. The studied literature showed that acne of various degrees occurs in 80-85% of people aged 12 to 25 years and that one of the main causes of the disease is microorganisms. Medicinal herbs such as *Abies koreana* essential oil, *Ammonia baccifera*, *Hibiscus syriacus*, *Quercus infectoria*, *Berberis aristata*, *Couroupita guianensis*, *Symplocos racemosa*, *Mucuna pruriens*, *Hemidesmus indicus*, *Coscinium fenestratum*, *Tephrosia purpurea*, *Euphorbia hirta*, *Curcubito pepo* and *Eclipta alba* are used to treat acne vulgaris. plants were found to be effective.

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